

My journey with Nina Thornhill

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Abstract: This article recounts my experience as a PhD candidate under Prof. Nina's supervision between January 2010 and January 2014. My thesis was entitled 'On extending process monitoring and diagnosis to the electrical and mechanical utilities: an advanced signal analysis approach'.

Keywords: PhD supervision, academic success, mentorship, empathy, role model

1. ON FIRST IMPRESSIONS

Professor Nina Thornhill was my PhD supervisor between 2010 and 2014. I had very successfully completed a BSc/MSc in Chemical Engineering in Portugal and had several proposals from local academic staff to pursue a PhD with them. Notwithstanding their high quality, I was looking for a top international institution, for a connection to industry problems, and for a cross-discipline challenge that would take me beyond core Chemical Engineering. Nina offered all this, but such a decisive step is still frightening at 23 years old. Nina, however, demonstrated her quality as a mentor right from the first email contact, promptly replying to my anxious questions with extensive explanations about the work in her group (extract shown in Fig. 1). She went further to help me write a research proposal for my PhD – something totally new to me at the time -, actually dedicating her time to turn my naïve attempt into something that became grant-worthy.

2. PROLIFIC YEARS

The four years I spent with Nina were memorable. They bore 10 scientific articles, a proud visit to the House of Commons to present my work and raise the profile of STEM (news piece in Fig. 2), two unforgettable industrial

internships with ABB Oslo and ABB Kraków in which, besides their technical influence on my work, I made close friends and experienced the real life of those institutions and countries. Then, the grand finale was my double win of the 2013 Chemical Engineering PhD Symposium which was the pivotal moment that started my career with Schlumberger (news piece in Fig. 3). All this I owe to Nina. At the end of the emotional ups-and-downs that come with a PhD I was confident with the quality of my work thanks to the support and opportunities for growth that Nina had offered me. Nina believed in me and challenged me from the start. She never told me the answer, but always helped me find it. Nina had a great influence in the way I came to present and write my research, and now that I am myself in a position of guiding others I take her example of empathy combined with thoroughness, a true will to develop others.

3. LEADERSHIP STYLE

There were a few implicit lessons that Nina transmitted to her mentees, should they be interested and paying attention. One of those is the possibility of being a technical leader or a leader in an organization without stopping being accessible and listening to everyone. I remember Nina mentioning in casual conversation, but with admiration, a few such people; but also herself was such type of role model. If there is one thing I am certain all her students will agree with is that Nina never placed herself above them, but instead led by inspiring and being present. The World could do more with this leadership.

4. ONE FINAL THANKS

In Fig. 4, I am standing proud with Nina and my partner Pedro on my graduation day. I cannot thank Nina enough for having made me reach that day with increased maturity and prepared for the career ahead. This, I believe, is what Nina would wish for all her students and what she has devoted herself to.

Applying to Imperial
Nina Thornhill <n.thornhill@imperial.ac.uk> 7 March 2009 at 22:06
Dear Ines
Hi, it is very nice to hear from you and I'm glad to have the opportunity to tell you more. The Process Automation research is within the Centre for Process Systems Engineering (CPSE) which involves two London universities - Imperial College in the South Kensington area of London and also University College London in Bloomsbury. I'm at Imperial having moved here from UCL two years ago, and what we're discussing here is admission to Imperial. The activities in the CPSE range across all scales from molecular systems engineering (e.g. modelling of hydrogen bonds and designing solvents), through process optimization (e.g. new designs for co-generation plants) to optimization in enterprise-wide systems which is where the supply chain activity comes in. There are about 6-7 academics in Imperial's Chemical Engineering department (lecturers and professors) involved in these activities and another 6 at UCL. There are also many close collaborators both in Chem Eng and from other departments such as Computing and EE Eng. I would say there is a greater emphasis on design than on process operations in CPSE, however the Process Automation research that I do is about the efficient operation of existing plant, and does not involve design. The attached WinZip archive includes the CPSE Annual Report from last year to give an idea. This year's Report is with the publisher, will be out in April.
The earlier e-mail gave some examples of the activities and I have also put some papers and articles into the attached WinZip archive, including two articles from ABB Review (HordChill...) which describe studies that used our methods and a review of the state of the art in the area of plant-wide disturbance analysis ThornhillKorhonen. Advances and new directions in plant-wide... If you open these up and skim read the abstracts and introductions they will give you an idea of the work. Also in the archive are papers from industrial authors who explain the industrial challenges and give examples. Finally, you can look inside a recent book written by U of Alberta co-authors and me, at the URL below. The case study chapter on page 253 may be interesting.
<http://www.amazon.co.uk/Diagnosis-Process-Nonlinearities-Valve-Stiction/dp/9540792236>
Signal analysis methods for process analysis are founded in two main mathematical areas. One is linear systems analysis including frequency response methods and spectral analysis. If you have ever looked at Fourier

series and Fourier transforms then you certainly have the necessary basics - it is not too difficult. The other area is random variable theory and statistics. Again, not too hard and there are courses available. Application of signal analysis to data from processes requires the above techniques, but above all it requires people who have a good in-depth understanding of the process behaviour (i.e. flow sheeting, dynamics). Therefore it is much easier for a chemical engineer to start doing process data analysis than for a signal analysis person to learn about processes. I hope this puts your mind at rest.

Some of the most interesting process data analysis at the moment concerns the way in which disturbances propagate from one plant to another on a large site via the site utilities (steam, water, fuel gas, electrical power system). I'm starting case studies on this topic with ABB and an operating company in Norway in July and there certainly are likely to be opportunities for industrial placements in that and similar projects. I think it is important for PhD students to have an industrial placement. Students who have had industrial placements include Margaret Bauer (Eastman Chemicals), Cylie Altheire (BP), Jerry Thambirajah (current student who is with National Grid right now), Torge Joran (current student who is going to BP soon), Lamia Benabbas (Lamia was a postdoc who spent several months with ABB in Oslo), Waqas Iqbal (current student, just started) will be going to ABB in Oslo.

You probably know that in UK universities gaining admission and gaining funding are quite separate. I'm thinking that if you are interested in a PhD it might be worth making an application for admission right away so as to get the ball rolling. If you write in the form that you are interested in working with me then I will be sure to get it. At that stage, if things look fine, then you could come over for an interview and take the opportunity to look around. Do please let me know ...

<http://www.imperial.ac.uk/chemicalengineering/courses/postgraduatephd>
Dario mentioned you might be trying for a scholarship from your government. Could you please kindly let me know more about it? The reason for asking is that success in gaining admission at Imperial does not guarantee funding, whereas a scholarship would provide financial support independently of Imperial. Scholars with independent funding have a more free choice of PhD topic than Imperial-supported students who generally have to deliver a specified piece of a pre-defined research plan.

Best wishes, looking forward to hearing from you
Nina Thornhill

At 23:44 05/03/2009, you wrote:

Fig. 1. First email sent to me by Nina.

Departmental PhD Research Symposium

Inês Cecílio giving her presentation

The Department of Chemical Engineering held the annual PhD Research Symposium on Friday 30th March 2013. It was a whole day event with oral and poster presentations from PhD students. Guests varied from Industrial companies, including CPSE Industrial Consortium Members, Faculty members, students and researchers. CPSE students were outstanding and did the Centre proud. Two of the **1st Prizes** for oral presentation went to **Inês Cecílio** who presented her work on "Detection and diagnosis of disturbances across natural gas processes and the electrical utility using advanced signal analysis." Many congratulations to Inês who was awarded not one but two first prizes - one from the Academic and Industrial panel and one from the student vote. This was the first time in the Symposium history that student votes as well as Academic and Industrial panel decisions were the same! **Eirini Sioukrou** won **3rd Prize** for her presentation "QM - CAMD: Advances in Computer-Aided Molecular Design of Solvents for Reactions." **David Garcia Münzer** was joint runner up for the poster category, 'Dynamic Cyclin Profiles as a Tool to Segregate the Cell Cycle.' with **Thapanar Suwanmajo**. "Multisite Phosphorylations as Complex Chemical Signal Processors." These outstanding students were congratulated for their wonderful presentations by their supervisors: Prof Nina Thornhill, Prof Claire Adjiman and Prof Amparo Galindo, Prof Sakis Mantalaris and Dr Krishnan.

Early career researchers descend on parliament

by Andrew Czyzewski, Simon Levey
29 April 2013

Miss Inês Cecílio, a PhD candidate in the Department of Chemical Engineering with Brian Iddon MP

Last month the House of Commons hosted a group of early career researchers, including 16 from Imperial, who presented their science to politicians.

As part of the SET for Britain event, held on 18 March, 180 presenters were entered into categories, namely engineering, biological and biomedical sciences, chemistry and physics after being shortlisted from hundreds of applicants.

On presenting his research, Dr Davide Fabozzi (Chemical Engineering), a Marie Curie Experienced Research Fellow, said: "It was a unique opportunity. My research deals with one of the greatest challenges of our era: the integration of renewable energy resources.

While my work addresses the scientific aspects of the problem, ultimately it is the politicians who set the policies for our future. I am hopeful that fruitful discussion may come from the interactions with MPs."

Miss Inês Cecílio, a PhD candidate also in the Department of Chemical Engineering (pictured with Brian Iddon MP), presented a poster on her research into new signal analysis methods for monitoring the production of natural gas. "It's a chance to help demystify the idea of science as unreachable and inapplicable, and to draw the attention of our leaders and the wider public to the key role of scientific research to social and economic growth."

Fig. 2. Imperial College news piece about the 2013 SET For Britain event at the House of Commons.

Fig. 3. CPSE newsletter article on the 2013 PhD Research Symposium.

Fig. 4. Proud Graduation Day - thank you Nina.